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D4.2 Publication on the smart job scheduler implementation

Work Package 4. Building blocks for a sustainable operating model.

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Executive Summary

Galaxy is currently using the Total Perspective Vortex (TPV) to schedule millions of jobs for hundred thousand users globally. While TPV has proven to be a robust meta-scheduling tool for Galaxy in the last years, there are areas of improvement that have been addressed in the EuroScienceGateway project:

1. Gathering live usage metrics from across the distributed computing endpoints connected to Galaxy in order to distribute the load across all sites.
2. Adding latitude and longitude attributes to data stores and computing endpoints to allocate jobs as close as possible to the location of the data
3. Visualizing job distribution across sites with an intuitive dashboard.

As a result the EuroScienceGateway project has developed two new tools:

1. TPV Broker for the efficient meta-scheduling of jobs taking into account real-time usage metrics and data-locality information
2. Galaxy Job Radar: a web dashboard to easily visualize the allocation of jobs across all sites

The EuroScienceGateway project has significantly improved the meta-scheduling of jobs for Galaxy, resulting in less waiting times for users to see their job completed and improving resource utilization across all sites.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
GJR	Galaxy Job Radar
HPC	High Performance Computing
TPV	Total Perspective Vortex

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Introduction

Galaxy processes millions of jobs for a user base of over 500,000 researchers worldwide, utilizing local HPC clusters, cloud environments, and remote computing infrastructures (such as Pulsar) to execute these jobs. The collection of computing resources to execute Galaxy jobs are called *destinations*. Currently, job scheduling is done by the Total Perspective Vortex (TPV), a system that performs the matchmaking between job requirements (in terms of required CPUs, amount of memory, GPUs, etc) and the capacity provided by destinations. The capacity provided by each destination is statically defined when the destination is added to Galaxy. This matchmaking based on static information is fast, and it has served Galaxy well in the recent past. However, the EuroScienceGateway project works towards improving this matchmaking or *meta-scheduling* in Galaxy on three different fronts:

1. Use up-to-date usage statistics from destinations, in addition to the static information already available in TPV
2. Add geolocation to data/object stores and destinations to enable locality-aware scheduling and, therefore minimize data movement
3. Visualize how jobs are dynamically scheduled across distributed destinations

The final aim is to improve job scheduling across all destinations, reducing execution time and improving resource utilization. This smart job scheduler is called *TPV Broker*.

The next section summarizes the implementation of the TPV Broker. The full details of this work have been submitted as a pre-print for a publication that can be accessed here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14936845>.

Proposed Approach: TPV Broker

The TPV Broker brings to Galaxy a meta-scheduling algorithm based on the geographical location of data and destinations, plus real-time statistics about the utilization of said destinations. To achieve this:

1. New geolocation attributes provide latitude and longitude coordinates of data/object stores and destinations. The goal is to schedule jobs as close as possible to the data and minimize data movement.
2. A centralized time-series database, relying on InfluxDB, collects resource utilization statistics through an opt-in producer-consumer script. The goal is to schedule jobs to destinations with more available capacity.

Figure 1 shows destinations spanning multiple countries pushing metrics to a central InfluxDB database. These metrics include: number of available CPUs, amount of available memory, and average system load. The TPV Broker queries InfluxDB to get up-to-date information about destinations, and this way allocates upcoming jobs for execution in the destinations that are less busy. The details of the meta-scheduling algorithm are presented in the publication.

Figure 1. Gathering of resource utilization across destinations using InfluxDB.

To visualize the meta-scheduling in action, an interactive dashboard has also been developed, called the *Galaxy Job Radar* (or GJR for short). Like TPV Broker, GJR also queries the InfluxDB to check how busy each destination is (Figure 1). GJR displays a pie chart per destination classifying jobs in the statuses *running*, *queued*, and *failed*, as reported by the local batch scheduler (Figure 2). This way, it is easier to identify how well each destination is performing.

Figure 2. Galaxy Job Radar displaying usage of Pulsar endpoints across Europe.

Conclusions

While the Total Perspective Vortex (TPV) meta-scheduler has successfully facilitated job scheduling in Galaxy, the development of the TPV Broker and Galaxy Job Radar within the EuroScienceGateway project aims to further enhance job allocation efficiency and system observability. The TPV Broker is designed to improve scheduling decisions by incorporating real-time resource tracking, dynamic ranking algorithms, and data locality optimizations, which could lead to better load distribution and reduced job wait times. Additionally, the producer-consumer model is expected to enable adaptive job routing based on live system metrics, potentially improving overall scheduling performance.

Moreover, Galaxy Job Radar provides an interactive visualization of job flow across distributed Pulsar endpoints, allowing administrators to monitor workload patterns, identify potential bottlenecks, and optimize resource allocation dynamically. These advancements are intended to improve job turnaround times and resource utilization, benefiting the global Galaxy user community. For further details on the implementation of these new tools, please refer to the pre-print at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14936845>.

